

A Comparative Study of Anxiety and Adjustment between Player and Non- Player Students

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Abstract—The objective of this study was to examine anxiety and adjustment between sportsmen and non-sportsmen students. Another objective of the study was to compare anxiety and adjustment between sportsmen and non-sportsmen students.

Methods: The subjects for the study were selected from the 60 male students (30 students participating in C.B.S.E. Cluster Championships and 30 students studying the school) in Mata Daan Kaur Public School, Delhi for session 2024-25. The age level of subjects was range from 15 to 18 years. To measure for this investigation was anxiety of Sportsmen and non-sportsmen students by Anxiety Scale developed by Dr. V. P. Sharma were administered and the investigation was adjustment of sportsmen and non-sportsmen students by Adjustment Inventory for school students developed by Dr. A. K. P. Sinha & Dr. R. P. Singh. To find out significant different of anxiety and adjustment between sportsmen and non-sportsmen students, t-test was used. The level of significance was set at .05 levels.

Results and Discussion: The results of the study show that there was no significant difference in anxiety between sportsmen and non-sportsmen students, whereas there was a significant difference in adjustment between sportsmen and non-sportsmen students.

Index Terms—Anxiety, Adjustment, Players and Non-Players

I. Introduction

As students, we often hear about how important it is to focus on our studies, marks and attend the classes but what about our mental and emotional health. Each and every student feels pressure in their life (exam stress, peer experiences or personal problem). This is where anxiety and adjustment come into life.

Anxiety is something everyone feel and face once in life (before an exam, before big performance, in public speaking or before any big event) and we can say it can be a natural response by human being, but it depends on level of anxiety if it became excessive or chronic it can affect our performance, confidence and day to day functioning. Those who face high anxiety can feel pain, fast heartbeat, and make poor decisions.

Anxiety is a natural human response to stress, fear and danger. Anxiety is a feeling of worry, nervousness, or fear that is often experienced in response to a perceived threat or stressful situation. It is a natural emotional reaction that everyone experiences from time to time – such as before exam, before any event, public speaking, or making important decisions. In psychological terms, anxiety can be defined as: A state of uneasiness and apprehension often about something with an uncertain outcome. Anxiety and Adjustment are critical psychological aspects affecting students' academic performance and overall wellbeing.

Now let's talk about Adjustment, adjustment means how we cooperate in any situation and deal with stress. If we struggle to adjust, it can be show up as emotional distress, frustration or even withdrawal from social situations. It also shows the ability of individuals to adapt to new people, places or any new situation. Every person has different actions on how to handle pressure, deal and any social gathering.

Adjustment means where an individual or person has the ability to adapt to the situation, norms and social environment. Adjustment is a vital component of an individual's overall well- being and psychological development. For good Adjustment people should have good control on their emotions (Like –anger, jealousy, anxiety and happiness). Adjustments help to build the self confidence, communication and social acceptance of an individual. Adjustment on students influences their performances.

Being a student today is stressful. On students there is pressure from everywhere from parents, teachers, exams, competition, and now from social media. In today's era, many students worry about marks, fitting in, or disappointing from someone. They may not share the things but they carry the weight inside them and it may cause anxiety, over thinking, low self esteem and sometimes even isolation. Those students also face a struggle to adjust to change like a new class, a strict teacher or in a group.

Physical Activities help to develop the students physically, mentally and emotionally. Teenagers face difficulty in school, making friends, fit and plans for the future and in this age feeling confused, nervous, or even lost during any situation is very normal. That's why we need physical activities in student's lifestyles (like playing sports, running, swimming). Sports give them a break from studies so they can feel relaxed and learn teamwork, leadership qualities and how to handle winning and losing. Sports also help them to be fit and active and feel lighter mentally. Sports overcome the mental stress, anxiety and depression, so they can focus on their studies and their future plans. It also helps them to deal with their emotions and build good habits so that it supports mental health for life.

II. Methodology

The subjects for the study were selected from the 60 male students (30 students participating in C.B.S.E. Cluster Championships and 30 students studying the school) in Mata Daan Kaur Public School, Delhi for session 2024-25. The age level of subjects was range from 15 to 18 years. To measure for this investigation was anxiety of Sportsmen and non-sportsmen students by Anxiety Scale developed by Dr. V. P. Sharma was administered and the investigation was adjustment of sportsmen and non-sportsmen students by Adjustment Inventory for school students developed by Dr. A. K. P. Sinha & Dr. R. P. Singh. To find out significant different of anxiety and adjustment between sportsmen and non-sportsmen students, t-test was used. The level of significance was set at .05 levels.

Results of the Study

To find anxiety between player and non-player students, descriptive statistics was used and presented in table-1.

TABLE-1
Descriptive statistics of anxiety between player and non-player students

	Players	Non-Players
Mean	61.83	62.57
Standard Deviation	10.75	8.44
Range	35	30
Minimum	43	45

Maximum	78	75
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It is evident from table no.1, which shows the mean value of anxiety for players was 61.83, whereas mean value for non-players was 62.57. This table shows the standard deviation value of anxiety for players was 10.75, whereas standard deviation value for non-players was 8.44. This table shows the range value of anxiety for players was 35, whereas the range value for non-players was 30. Table also repeats that the minimum value of anxiety for players was 43, whereas minimum value for non-players was 45. This table shows the maximum value of anxiety for players was 78, whereas maximum value for non-players was 75.

To find anxiety between player and non-player students, t-ratio statistics was used and presented in table-2.

TABLE-2
T-ratio of the means of anxiety between player and non-player students

	Game		t-ratio
	Players	Non-Players	
Mean	61.83	62.57	-.294*
S.D	10.75	8.44	

*Insignificant at .05 level
t-value required to be significant at 58 df = 2.00

It is evident from table-2 that insignificant difference was found between the mean scores of players and non-players in relation to anxiety as the t-value was found -.294. This was a lower value than the required value at .05 level of significance.

The scores are also illustrated in the figure-1.

To find adjustment between player and non-player students, descriptive statistics was used and presented in table-3.

TABLE-3
Descriptive statistics of adjustment between player and non-player students

	Players	Non-Players
Mean	32.33	38.70
Standard Deviation	9.74	7.75
Range	41	31
Minimum	17	26
Maximum	58	57

It is evident from table no.3, which shows the mean value of adjustment for players was 32.33, whereas mean value for non-players was 38.70. This table shows the standard deviation value of adjustment for players was 9.74, whereas standard deviation value for non-players was 7.75. This table shows the range value of adjustment for players was 41, whereas range value for non-players was 31. The table also repeats that the minimum value of adjustment for players was 17, whereas minimum value for non-players was 26. This table shows the maximum value of adjustment for players was 58, whereas maximum value for non-players was 57.

To find adjustment between player and non-player students, t-ratio statistics was used and presented in table-4.

TABLE-4
T-ratio of the means of adjustment between player and non-player students

Game			t-ratio
	Players	Non-Players	-2.802*
Mean	32.33	38.70	
S.D	9.74	7.75	

*Insignificant at .05 level
t-value required to be significant at 58 df =2.00

It is evident from table-4 that a significant difference was found between the mean scores of players and non-players in relation to adjustment as the t-value was found -2.802. This was a higher value than the required value at .05 level of significance.

The scores are also illustrated in the figure-2.

III. Bibliography

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